

AN OVERVIEW OF ANTENNA ARRAY FOR SCIENTIFIC DATA DOWNLINK IN CHINA'S LUNAR AND DEEP-SPACE EXPLORATION MISSIONS. X. Y. Zhu¹, C.L. Li¹, W. Zuo¹ and W. L. Chen¹, ¹National Astronomical Observatories, Chinese Academy of Science, Beijing, China.

Introduction: China's lunar and deep-space exploration program, formally established in 2004, has evolved from initial orbital reconnaissance to complex surface operations and sample return missions. The Chang'e series illustrates this technological leap: from the orbital imaging of Chang'e-1 (2007) and the soft landing of Chang'e-3 (2013) to the historic lunar sample return by Chang'e-5 (2020)[1]. In the domain of interplanetary exploration, the Tianwen-1 mission demonstrated unprecedented versatility by successfully executing orbiting, landing, and roving on Mars within a single mission architecture. The program is now entering a new era of sustained presence and extended reach. Key ongoing and upcoming initiatives include the Tianwen-2 asteroid sampling mission (launched May 2025) and the Chang'e-7 expedition to the lunar south pole (planned for 2026) to search for water ice. Looking further ahead, the strategic roadmap encompasses ambitious objectives such as Mars sample return and exploration of the Jovian system[2]. This rapid expansion in mission scope and scientific complexity has precipitated an exponential growth in data volume, necessitating a corresponding paradigm shift in ground-based infrastructure for robust scientific data downlink. To acquire more scientific data, the National Astronomical Observatories of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (NAOC), which oversees the Ground Research and Application System (GRAS) for China's lunar and deep-space exploration program, has implemented antenna arraying to receive downlinked scientific data from the spacecraft.

Arraying Configuration: The antenna array consists of four antennas located at three ground stations under the NAOC. Among them, the Miyun Ground Station, situated in Bulaotun Town, Miyun District, Beijing, is equipped with two large-aperture antennas: GRAS-1 and GRAS-3. The GRAS-1 antenna has a diameter of 50 meters and is a wheel-track alt-azimuth prime-focus antenna, completed in 2006. The GRAS-3 antenna has a diameter of 40 meters and is a turntable alt-azimuth Cassegrain antenna, completed in 2016. The Kunming Ground Station, located on Fenghuang Mountain in the eastern suburbs of Kunming City, Yunnan Province in southwestern China, is equipped with one GRAS-2 antenna. The GRAS-2 antenna has a diameter of 40 meters and is a turntable alt-azimuth Cassegrain antenna, completed in 2006. The Wuqing Ground Station, located in Daliang Town, Wuqing District, Tianjin, is equipped with one GRAS-4 antenna. The GRAS-4 antenna has a diameter of 70 meters and is a wheel-track alt-azimuth Cassegrain antenna, completed in 2020[3]. Two operational modes are supported by the antenna array: single-antenna mode and arraying mode. In the single-antenna configuration, each antenna operates independently, enabling the simultaneous tracking of different spacecraft for data downlink. In the arraying config-

uration, the signals from the target spacecraft received by each antenna are frequency-converted, sampled, digitized, and then transmitted via a dedicated fiber-optic network to the data processing center at the NAOC headquarters on Datun Road, Chaoyang District, Beijing, for coherently combination and demodulation. The geographical distribution of the four antennas and the data center is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1. The geographical distribution of antenna arraying.

Future Development: In previous missions, the S and X bands were primarily used as the communication frequencies for data transmission to Earth. For the Chang'e-7 mission, the communication frequency for downlink data transmission has been upgraded to the Ka-band. Accordingly, the GRAS-3 and GRAS-4 antennas are currently being retrofitted to integrate Ka-band reception capabilities. Furthermore, to meet the exponentially growing data return requirements of future deep-space exploration endeavors, two new 50-meter aperture antennas, designated GRAS-5 and GRAS-6, are planned for construction at the Miyun and Wuqing stations, respectively.

References:

- [1] Li C. L. et al. (2023) Science China Earth Sciences, 66(11), 2399–2418.
- [2] Zhang R. Q. et al. (2025) Sci Sin-Phys Mech Astron 55, 279501
- [3] Kong D. Q. et al. (2020) Journal of Astronautics, 41(7), 948-958